

LOOKING THROUGH THE LENS OF TEACHERS' LIFE-WORK IN FAR-FLUNG AREAS: A HERMENEUTIC PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Looking through the Lens of Teachers' Life-work in Far-Flung Areas: A Hermeneutic Phenomenological Study

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ABSTRACT

This study is qualitative research using hermeneutic qualitative phenomenological design which aimed to interpret the life-work experience of teachers in far-flung areas. The objective of this approach was to analyze the life-work experience of teachers. The aforementioned experiences of the participants reflect their real-life work encounters, thereby facilitating the formulation of conclusions regarding the nature of far-flung areas as a phenomenon. The objective of this study was to analyze the work experiences of teachers with a specific focus on Bagong Elementary School and Magaswe Elementary School. Teachers who are employed in far-flung locations have faced a multitude of difficulties. By employing the hermeneutic phenomenological approach, researchers have interpreted and analyzed their experiences. Findings indicate that teachers exhibit varying levels of experience and distinct challenges when teaching in far-flung schools. The professional experiences of teachers throughout their careers were Teaching: A fusion of gratitude and dedication, the greatness of community, and gratifying experience. Moreover, the greatness of community that works together in harmony and unity elucidates the support they received from the community, and teacher's gratifying experience who ignites the flame of knowledge in the eager learner gives rewarding for the teachers when they see the eagerness of the pupils to learn. Regarding on challenges, remoteness and inadequate resources were the Arduous journey experienced by the participants, prevalent among all teachers assigned in these locations. The study found that far-flung school teachers are intrinsically motivated despite their daily challenges. Their psychological resources—passion, grit, love for their pupils, and community support—give them intrinsic incentive to overcome work challenges. Insufficient educational learning resources must be addressed to help teachers deliver lessons efficiently. Thus, far-flung schoolchildren receive the same educational resources as urban schoolchildren. This can encourage far-flung teachers to appreciate their jobs and stay.

Keywords: *life-work, far-flung, lens of teachers, hermeneutic phenomenology*

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INTRODUCTION

‘TEACHER’ the word itself includes ‘Teach’ which means “GURU” who shares the experience, knowledge, and skills to others for a better-educated world. Teaching is the most desirable profession nowadays. The importance of the Teaching Profession includes fun and learning together. Being in the teaching profession does not sharing only of knowledge, sometimes teachers themselves learn something new with teaching experience. Teachers play a vital role in student’s life by helping them achieve their goals. Therefore, choosing the Teaching Profession offers endless career opportunities (edmonger, 2021).

The difficulty of finding enough qualified teachers to work in rural and regional schools persists. The study of Burke and Buchanan (2022) look into effective incentives for recruiting teachers to rural and remote schools in New South Wales (NSW), Australia, that are challenging to teachers. Teacher staff shortages, inexperience, and turnover put children in these schools at a disadvantage compared to their metropolitan counterparts. The research uncovered different approaches that might be taken to entice teachers with varying degrees of expertise and levels of dedication to work in far-flung areas. Rental subsidies, annual retention rewards, additional personal leave, professional development days, and local allowances are provided to keep teachers. It is imperative for parents to be actively engaged in the organization of their children's learning environment and program. It is imperative that adequate support be extended to pupils to enable them to effectively face the challenges of remote education. (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020).

With these setting, it is important to explore the experiences of teachers who are teaching in the far-flung areas.

Research Questions

This study interpreted and gave meaning to the different life-work experiences of the teachers in Bagong Elementary School and Magaswe Elementary School. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the life-work experience of the teachers assigned in far-flung areas of Ormoc City, Leyte?
2. How do teaching in far-flung areas influence the teachers as professional?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result of the study. Each person’s experience is still unique even through people are in the same area or going through a situation that is very similar to one another. During the course of a lifetime, it is not uncommon for a person to face both happy and bad experiences. The emergence of each of these occurrences was brought about as a result of a convergence of a number of different kinds of contributing variables. What is significant, however, is the knowledge that may be obtained from that event and applied to the building of a new path in one's life experiences. This is what makes the experience meaningful.

In this study, there are two major themes. First is Valuable life work experiences with three sub-themes: Teaching a fusion of gratitude and dedication, The greatness of community, and Gratifying experience. The second is the Arduous Journey with two sub-themes namely: Remoteness and Inadequate resources.

Valuable Life Work Experience

The concept of work-life balance encompasses the notion of work, which comprises both the psychological and physical exertions required to meet the demands of one's job (Bello & Tanko, 2020). They note that the phrase "work life balance" gained widespread recognition during the period spanning from 1986 to 1990. The term is frequently employed in both academic research and organizational contexts, particularly in the field of human resource management, with the aim of promoting the welfare of employees.

Sometimes the things that happen to us at work require us out of our comfort zones and force us to deal with challenging facts or difficult situations that we never thought we have to deal with. This can be a very humbling experience. Some of these circumstances might even cause us to reconsider our views or our capacity to comprehend the perspectives of others.

Teachers in far-flung areas need to walk kilometers of rough terrain or trek into the mountains to get to school and to teach pupils. They are given many other administrative tasks than focusing on a teaching role. They get blamed whenever there is a lack of pupils' required documents. Since this would affect their performance evaluation, teachers would rather spend their own money to help pupils acquire their lacking documents. Teachers must shoulder their expenses during the home visitation of pupils who usually live in secluded places. They also shoulder athletes' expenses due to parents' lack of support. (Felongco, 2022). Teachers are constantly challenged to provide quality education. Far-flung schools in the Philippines still face a shortage of teaching resources, and the quality of education received by pupils depends on learning environments and facilitators. The teacher's performance is affected due to various stress and challenges in providing quality education (Usman, Y.D. and Madudili, C.G. 2019).

Teaching: A Fusion of Gratitude and Dedication

Some of the participants indicated that many teachers are attracted to teaching because of their passion for children or because of their own drive to learn. Teachers become educators because they want to make a difference. Instead of viewing being a teacher as a necessity, the younger generation view it as an opportunity to build a better future for themselves. It is becoming increasingly socially acceptable to interact with the children of today in order to instill in them virtuous behaviors and educational ideas, which makes teaching a more joyful profession (Siliguri, 2018). Hence, many people who feel obliged to teach or who see teaching as a vitally significant part of their lives have a strong enthusiasm for the profession. According to the definition, a passion is "a strong inclination or attraction for an activity that one appreciates, values, and in which one invests time and effort.

The Greatness of Community

This is the second sub-theme under the theme of Valuable life experience, the greatness of community. These findings show that the community play a big role in the education of pupils

in far-flung areas. Results show that the people in the community are very approachable, hospitable, kind, and very supportive in school. They are very supportive to the teachers; whatever instructions teachers give concerning school tasks; the community readily make themselves available and work collaboratively with the school. Further, parents always support the teachers and the school and the community especially the Barangay officials always show full support to the school if they are treated well. Moreover, the community especially the parents are friendly; if you ask them to do something, they easily respond to the tasks without complaints and they are very industrious and worked very hard to provide the family.

Based from the sharing, the majority of the teachers who participated in the study stated that they find teaching in far-flung areas to be more satisfying than teaching in urban areas. They were able to differentiate between situations and have experience working in areas with varying levels. In addition, educators experienced a deeper sense of connection and dedication to the pupils, which enabled them to enjoy the personal fulfillment that comes with playing the role of a coach in addition to that of a traditional educator (Brillantes and Nebria, 2021). The principal, the teachers, and the community all play an important role in the formation of a good grade school. According to Rahmadi and Istiqamah (2010), this method is referred to as the "bottom up strategy of parent to teacher association" (PTA). It was explained by Nachtigal (n.d.) that in order for rural schools to become important players in community development, we need to do the following: (1) rethink how we think about the purposes of schooling; (2) shift the focus of the curriculum, at least in part from a generic, national-focused curriculum to one that focuses on the local community context; (3) educate pupils so that they have the skills to create their own jobs rather than being prepared only to find jobs; and (4) use the resources that are available.

Findings imply that the community exhibits a hospitable and benevolent demeanor, while also demonstrating a strong commitment to supporting the educational pursuits of its members. The teachers receive backing from the community and guardians, who comply with their directives regarding academic assignments. In far-flung areas, receiving support from parents can be facilitated by exhibiting kindness towards them. Providing favorable treatment to stakeholders, particularly Barangay officials, can result in their endorsement and backing. It is imperative to exhibit proficient pedagogical abilities. On each occasion when the teacher requires assistance, the community exhibits a high degree of cooperation. Individuals who exhibit positive character traits such as kindness, respectfulness, and self-discipline tend to engage in school-related activities and offer assistance where needed. Additionally, they adhere to other requests made by the school. Community members who exhibit amicable behavior, particularly parents, are likely to comply with requests without expressing dissatisfaction. There has been no discernible shift in the attitude of parents. The responsibility of school lies primarily with the parents of the children, particularly the mothers. The teachers can rely on their constant availability.

Gratifying Experience

This is another sub-theme of the theme Valuable life experience, Gratifying experience. Teachers often encounter difficulties in engaging their pupils due to the common error of committing the "About A Topic" fallacy. The error of 'About A Topic' pertains to the act of instructing on a given subject matter solely by providing information 'About A Topic'. The proposed solution entails prioritizing personalized instruction geared towards the pupil's needs rather than imparting general knowledge 'about a topic'. The pedagogical approach should

prioritize the immediate perception of the instructional content's utility by the pupils (Horkff, T. n.d.). Demonstrating a benefit has the potential to generate a sense of longing or aspiration. When an individual experience a sense of longing or yearning, it results in capturing their focus and maintaining their engagement.

Arduous Journey

Teaching is a journey. This journey is a mixture of different experiences. The second Theme is Arduous Journey. Arduous is the difficulty encountered by the teachers while teaching in far-flung area. These are the difficult and tiring experiences of the teachers as they journey in their teaching professions. The characteristic of being difficult and, as a result, requiring a great deal of effort and energy to accomplish is referred to as arduousness (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.). In this theme, there are two sub-themes, Remoteness and Inadequate resources.

Education in far-flung areas is a global concern (Chunling, 2011) nonetheless, there are significant educational disparities between rural and urban schools (Lingam and Lingam, 2013), which can have severe repercussions for both society and the economy in the long run (Braun et al., 2006).

In the course of my research, the challenges faced by the participants when teaching in a far-flung area were the concern of how easily they could travel to and from the school away from their home. Distant schools cannot be compared to schools in urban areas. According to research conducted, pupils attending schools located in far-flung areas encounter a greater number of challenges in their personal lives as well as in their educational experiences. These challenges range from being impoverished to having less opportunities. In addition, aspects of the school such as its size and location are relevant factors to consider. Our pupils are forced to walk long miles on foot and endure facing serious challenges, particularly in far-flung areas that have limited physical accessibility to schools, which can make it difficult for learners to get a fundamental education. Our pupils who live in rural areas typically must lug their backpacks behind them as they trek for an hour or two, scale hills and mountains, and traverse rivers on makeshift bridges on their way to and from school on a daily basis, regardless of the climate change whether it is boiling hot or pouring down rain.

Experiences constitute an essential part of professional life as teachers. Teachers encounter life changes, and each of them have a unique manner of coping with their experiences. The challenges they encounter in teaching in far-flung areas and the love to serve pupils made life meaningful. Although, they suffer apprehension, disappointment, tension, a lack of self-confidence, feelings of incompleteness, dependency, and an inability to cope with the circumstances that they faced on daily lives, teachers also were the hope of pupils' future. With this, teachers have the potential to stimulate enhancement in preparation for the hopeful progress in the cognitive, spiritual, social, and personal life of our learners, and the comprehension and insights gained on their professional opportunities and challenges (Bilbao, 2012).

Remoteness

This is the first sub-theme, Remoteness. It has been observed that the primary barrier that prevents teachers from working in far-flung areas is physical distance. Knowing that they

would be assigned to schools situated on the mountains, many of them experienced difficulty and problems on their journey. Perhaps, this is the reason why it is assigned to younger teachers.

In the sub-theme remoteness, findings show that experience of the teachers in far-flung areas was that the route to the far-flung school is mountainous or steep and the transportation was a bit different from their previous station. However, they are still grateful considering that they were given the item or a permanent teaching position. Teachers thought that they have to work despite the distance since this is what they are called for. The far-flung areas is really challenging, an arduous journey especially during rainy season as well as risky given that the road in going to school is very rough and bumpy. Lastly, teachers are not comfortable because of the distance and inaccessibility.

Teaching is recognized as the most prestigious profession. Participant seven sees that studying in distant classrooms is slightly different from learning in low-lying locations, and he feels a strong sense of satisfaction upon realizing he has been a part of the children's educational experience. According to Barcena (2018), it is quite difficult for teachers to be allocated in far-flung areas because they would confront a range of uncomfortable modes of transportation. This makes the assignment very demanding. If the weather is bad, the job gets more difficult. They would have to resort to hiking because the river is too dangerous for them to cross, and hiking is more difficult for them. The sticky mud, hopping over canals and hiking the diverse terrain, and walking through high grasses with perspiration dripping from their foreheads while carrying their food supplies and other requirements for the entire week were some of the experiences of the teachers. In spite of the circumstances, teachers in far-flung areas have not stopped putting on happy faces and maintaining an upbeat attitude. They do this out of a love for their work and in order to inspire the lives of the pupils who are patiently waiting for the beginning of each new week to receive their love and care. These pupils believe that education will somehow improve their lives.

Inadequate resources

The second sub-theme under the theme Arduous journey was Inadequate resources. These findings show that the school lack the facilities such as absence of oval in sports and in terms of academics, no computer laboratory and no computer units. School lacks technology and sports equipment. It was found out that the sports which are familiar to the pupils in far-flung areas are the only sports that they engage in the school while those schools in the city are exposed to many sports where they have new and complete sports equipment. This makes the experience of pupils in far-flung areas different among the students in the urban school. Further, participants said that it was never easy for teachers to go up in a mountainous area and go down to the city just to attend the seminar.

Educational resources have a favorable impact on pupils' academic achievement. Quality school facilities should always be available for teachers to do their tasks and assist students in learning and achieving efficiently. The participants faced lack of facilities and learning materials difficulties and challenges in providing quality education to the pupils due to the inaccessibility and supply of learning facilities and materials. Consequently, a shortage of resources in the classroom may be extremely stressful for both pupils and teachers. Not only are pupils and teachers in misery, but they are also unable to study to their full capacity due to a lack of resources.

CONCLUSION

Based from the results of the study it is concluded that teachers in far-flung schools are intrinsically motivated despite of the challenging experiences which confront them every day as they report to their remote station. This intrinsic motivation emanates from their psychological resources describing their abilities to manage various obstacles at work founded with passion, grit, love for their pupils and community support. It is essential that the concerns on the insufficient educational learning resources be addressed to facilitate teachers' efficiency in the lesson delivery. Thus, pupils in the far-flung areas be benefited with the same educational learning resources with those pupils studying in urban schools. This factor can further motivate teachers to love their profession and stay in their respective remote station.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to:

1. Increase the number of participants in order to investigate the influence of culture on teaching in remote areas. This research only looks at individuals who reside in the same culture, or in the same region.
2. Conduct comparative research on the life-work experiences of teachers who work in both urban and rural settings.
3. Present the findings to DepEd to encourage the distribution of learning materials simultaneously both in rural and urban areas.
4. Sustain the support coming from the barangay officials in far-flung areas be sustained to assist teachers' safety in reporting to school and in going home to their respective places.
5. Organize stress reduction activities for teachers in far-flung areas to maintain their physical and mental wellbeing.

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